

From Global South to Global Commons

Diamond Open Access

Lrhoul Hanae

School of Information Sciences. Morocco

Bengauluru 03/02/2026

- **Cognitive justice:** equity and multilingualism as core challenges
- African & Arab Journals: What **Infrastructure** Gaps Reveal
- **Sustaining** Diamond OA: A Practical Roadmap

Cognitive justice

Cognitive Justice: Africa as a multilingual and multi-epistemic space;

Shared scientific sovereignty (Decolonizing knowledge);

Scientific Cooperation and Co-Construction of Knowledge as a Common Good.

« the right of different knowledges to coexist » **Shiv Visvanathan**

Accessibility et visibilité

Affirming equity through the recognition of local and multilingual knowledge;

Strengthening the global visibility of African research;

Positioning Diamond Open Access as a pathway to reduce asymmetries in scholarly communication.

Web of science: 983 219 articles

Open Alex: 1 787 000 articles

Publish or perish Vs scientific integrity

A BUMPER YEAR FOR RETRACTIONS

Retraction notices in 2023 have passed 10,000, largely because of more than 8,000 retractions by Hindawi.

OAD transparency tracabilite

Predatory pulisher

Over 39,000 withdrawals in 2025

Publish or perish: Publication in indexed journals

Scientific sovereignty

- Diamond Open Access oriented towards the public good ;
- Public policies that protect bibliodiversity, ensure discoverability and enhance the quality and visibility of journals;
- Stable, long term funding.

Source: COKI Climate Dash Demo

IF WE ARE GOING TO SOLVE THE WORLD'S GREATEST CHALLENGES, **THE KNOWLEDGE ABOUT THEM MUST BE OPEN**

Mapping the visibility and openness of African and Arab journals

Visibility of African journals

Répartition des étoiles par pays

Part relative de chaque niveau d'étoile (de 1 à 6) attribué aux revues scientifiques dans chaque pays, selon le modèle d'évaluation à 5 étoiles.

■ 1 étoile ■ 2 étoiles ■ 3 étoiles ■ 4 étoiles ■ 5 étoiles ■ 6 étoiles

Le modèle 5 étoiles de classification des revues

Aventurier, P., Lrhoul, H., Azilan, I., Barnoussi, N.
Enjeux d'internationalisation des revues scientifiques africaines

Données en cours de publication dans la revue Data et copus

African journal: Diamond Open Access

Low prevalence of Diamond Open Access, linked to an editorial model structured around APCs, observed across disciplines.

Diamond OA is gaining visibility

Most African journals are already Diamond

But visibility, infrastructure, and funding remain fragile.

AJOL: Diamond Open Access

Répartition des revues africaines en Open Access et Diamond Open Access sur AJOL, par pays

Scientific journals in the Arab region

The priority action is infrastructure and governance

Innovative Research in Information Sciences

**Hanae
LRHOUL**

**Nadia
BARNOUSSI**

**Amine
DALIL**

**Najat
AACHICH**

**Sanae
OUAHBI**

**Pascal
AVENTURIER**

Roadmap for an Open Scientific Ecosystem

National Open Science Policy;

Governance, quality and editorial transparency;

Sustainable infrastructures and international standards (PIDs, High-Quality Metadata);

Map and analyze African scholarly output and national research priorities.

Reform research assessment systems in line with CoARA.

Open Science in Morocco

- Open Access Diamond Portal (North africa)
- BNRM Academy (Open Science)
- Partnership with Laval University

Strategic perspectives: skills and training

Collage of posters and documents related to digital literacy and research data management, featuring logos like 'bcftools' and 'ISDS'.

Les licences Creative Commons
Création et indexation des revues électroniques dans le DOAJ

Les jeudis de l'AIFBD
16 mars à 13h (GMT)

Pr. Kamel Belhamei
Ambassadeur et rédacteur en chef DOAJ

Masterclass PENS'IA
Transformation des Pratiques dans l'Enseignement Supérieur à l'Ere de l'Education Ouverte et de l'Intelligence Artificielle

16 ET 17 JUIN 2023 09:00AM - 16:00AM FACULTÉ DES SCIENCES DE SFAX

Speakers: Dr. Souhail SHEKAA, Dr. Khoulid BERRADA, Dr. Hennes LENOUE, Dr. Corinne Amel ZAYANI, Dr. Riadh BEN MANSOUR, Dr. Imraj AYADI.

Gérer les données de la recherche
Un nouveau service des Bibliothèques

Pascal Aventurier
Institut de recherche pour le développement

Jeudi 8 mars à 13h (Heure Maroc)

DataCite au service de la science ouverte
améliorer la disponibilité des productions scientifiques transparentes

20 novembre à 12h (Heure Maroc)

Speakers: Prof. Leif Johansson, Mohamed Mustafa.

Conclusion

- ✓ Diamond OA is not just No APCs
- ✓ A commitment to cognitive justice
- ✓ Requires coherent governance, robust infrastructure, and sustainable funding
- ✓ Needs aligned incentives (recognition, evaluation, quality).

Thank you